

BERYLLIUM FLUORIDES. PART I. STUDIES ON HYDROLYSIS OF FLUOBERYLLATE ION (BeF_4^{2-}) BY CONDUCTIVITY AND THERMOMETRY

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By conductivity, thermometry and chemical methods it has been shown that the primary reaction between caustic soda and fluoberyllate ion occurs according to the equation : $\text{BeF}_4^{2-} + 2\text{OH}^- = \text{Be}(\text{OH})_2 + 4\text{F}^-$; the secondary reaction, *i.e.* the dissolution of $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ in excess of alkali, occurs subsequently, forming beryllate ion; no indication of the formation of $[\text{BeF}_3\text{OH}]^{2-}$ has been found.

The fluoberyllates of alkali metals were known from the time of Marignac (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1873, *iv*, 30, 45). Previously these compounds were regarded as double salts of alkali metal fluorides and beryllium fluoride. The identity of BeF_4^{2-} as a complex anion and its isomorphism with SO_4^{2-} ion were recognised and established by Sarkar and Rây (this *Journal*, 1929, 6, 987) and Rây (*Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1931, 201, 289).

Recently Mitra (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 241) published his thermometric studies on the hydrolysis of BeF_4^{2-} . As the data published by Mitra are incomprehensible from the light of the work done by the present author, the results, obtained by the author, are recorded in this communication along with the data that have been found by repeating the experiment with the same quantities of substances recorded by Mitra (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium fluoberyllate was prepared in the conventional way from freshly precipitated $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ and adding a slight excess of KHF_2 to the required amount. It was recrystallised from water and washed with water and alcohol. After drying in an air-oven at 110° , it was analysed by standard methods for fluorine and found to conform to the formula K_2BeF_4 . Other reagents used were of A. R. quality.

The conductivities of solutions were measured by Philips' conductivity measuring bridge, type GM 4249. The conductivity vessel consisted of a polyethylene beaker. The glass stems of the two platinised electrodes were carefully covered with wax. Potassium fluoberyllate solution was taken in the beaker and caustic soda solution was added from a burette; the solution was stirred with a plastic rod. Curves I and II (Fig. 1) show the conductometric titration results. The change of conductance after each addition was plotted against respective volumes of caustic soda solution added.

The thermometric titration set up was fitted according to Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1921, 18, 324) and titration was done taking all the precautions as laid down by him. Potassium fluoberyllate solution was taken in the Dewar flask and caustic soda solution was added from a burette. The change in temperature after each addition of alkali was noted with a Beckmann thermometer. The thermometric titration results are represented in curves III, IV and V (Fig. 2). In curves III and IV the total change

of temperature, $(T - T_0)$, was plotted against the volume of caustic soda solution added. Curve V was obtained with the same data of curve III after making volume correction according to Chatterjee (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 356); in this curve total temperature change for a constant volume,

$$(T - T_0) \times (V_0 + \Delta V) / V_0$$

was plotted against the volume of caustic soda solution added. Curve IV represents the data obtained by repeating with the quantities of K_2BeF_4 and NaOH recorded by Mitra (*loc.cit.*). As was written by him, the solution of K_2BeF_4 was made by shaking in minimum volume of water (approx. 90 c.c.) in a 100 c.c. volumetric flask and was transferred into the Dewar flask. The volumetric flask was washed several times with small amounts of water and the washings were added to the Dewar flask. As the exact volume of K_2BeF_4 solution after the dilution was not known, similar curve like the curve V could not be drawn with the data of curve IV.

For investigating the formation of K_2BeF_4OH (as suggested by Mitra, *loc.cit.*, during the addition of NaOH to K_2BeF_4), 0.4804 g. of K_2BeF_4 was taken in solution (in minimum amount of water) in a beaker and 25.2 c.c. of NaOH (0.1169 N) was added to it dropwise with constant stirring so that the molar ratio of K_2BeF_4 : NaOH was 1:1. Gelatinous precipitate (A) was found to appear almost from the beginning of the addition of caustic soda. Paper pulp was added to the solution and it was filtered carefully by suction through a rapid filtration quantitative filter paper (containing paper pulp) placed on a No. 3 sintered glass funnel. The filter paper was not washed to avoid the possibility of hydrolysis of the product (if any) in the precipitate. The filter paper was pressed with the head of a glass rod and was then ignited and fused with Na_2CO_3 . The melt was taken in solution by hot water and the beryllium oxide (B) was freed of all soluble salts by leaching with hot water and then estimated. The amount of Be (13.07 mg.) calculated from (B) was found to weigh almost half of the total beryllium in the K_2BeF_4 taken. The filtrate after separation of (B) was found to contain almost no fluorine by PbClF method. The filtrate (C), obtained after separation of (A), was evaporated to dryness in a platinum basin and then fused with Na_2CO_3 (D). The BeO from (D) was estimated and the amount of Be (12.31 mg.), calculated from this, was also found to weigh almost half of the total amount of beryllium in the K_2BeF_4 taken. From the filtrate of this carbonate fusion (D), fluorine was estimated by PbClF method and found to be 209.9 mg. Thus, almost all of the fluorine of the K_2BeF_4 taken was in the filtrate (C) and the ratio of Be and fluorine in (C) was found to be 1:8. The total amounts of Be (25.38 mg.) and F (209.9 mg.), which were found out in the above experiments, were slightly less than the actual amounts of Be (26.5 mg.) and F (223.8 mg.) contained in the K_2BeF_4 taken. As the author's intention was to find out only the ratios of Be and F in the gelatinous precipitate (A) and in the filtrate (C), the beaker of precipitation, the sintered funnel and the Büchner flask were not washed because this was thought to be unnecessary. Thus, the low results obtained above can be accounted for. So, from this experiment it was found that when K_2BeF_4 and NaOH were mixed in equimolar amounts, half of the total K_2BeF_4 was decomposed with the precipitation of $Be(OH)_2$, leaving the other half unchanged, and no K_2BeF_4OH was formed in the process.

DISCUSSION

It is observed from the conductometric titration curves I and II that the inflection points correspond to the molar ratios of K_2BeF_4 : NaOH as 1 : 2, so that the reaction occurs according to the equation

FIG. 1

Curve I: 100 c.c. of 0.001 M- K_2BeF_4 soln. + 0.1 M-NaOH soln.

II: 50 c.c. of 0.0404 M- K_2BeF_4 + 0.808M-NaOH soln.

FIG. 2

Curve III: 100 c.c. of $M/15$ - K_2BeF_4 soln. + 2.436 M-NaOH.

IV: 100 c.c. (approx) soln. containing 1.1023 g. of K_2BeF_4 + 2.0223 M-NaOH.
V: 100 c.c. of $M/15$ - K_2BeF_4 soln. + 2.436 M-NaOH (plotted after vol. correction).

In the thermometric titration curves III and IV two breaks are found to appear. The first and second breaks correspond respectively to the molar ratios of K_2BeF_4 : NaOH = 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. The first break was explained by Mitra (*loc. cit.*) as due to the formation of K_2BeF_3OH . But it is noticed that when curve V is drawn with the same data of curve III after making volume correction according to Chatterjee (*loc. cit.*), the break at 1:1 disappears. It can be pointed out in this connection that the data represented by Mitra (*loc. cit.*) are not in agreement with those of the present author and are not understandable as can be seen by comparing with the present one. It will be observed in curve V that the inflection point occurs at molar ratio of K_2BeF_4 : NaOH = 1 : 2 and then temperature gradually falls probably due to the formation of beryllate ion by the gradual dissolution of $Be(OH)_2$ in excess of alkali; the reaction occurring probably is an endothermic one.

Again, by the addition of one mole of NaOH to one mole of K_2BeF_4 and analysing the products (*vide supra*) it was found out that $Be(OH)_2$ was precipitated by decomposition of K_2BeF_4 according to equation (1) and no K_2BeF_3OH was formed in the process.

So, from the above evidence it has been definitely shown that the primary reaction between caustic soda and fluoberyllate ion occurs according to equation (1) and the secondary reaction, *i.e.* the dissolution of $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ in excess of alkali, occurs subsequently, forming beryllate ion no indication of the formation of $[\text{BeF}_2\text{OH}]^-$ ion has been found.

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